

SILVANUS: AN INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFORMATION PLATFORM FOR WILDFIRE MANAGEMENT – NORTH EVIA PILOT AREA

Georgios Sakkas¹, Vassiliki Varela¹, Iosif Vourvachis², Alexandros Giordanis², Stelios Andreadis³, **Ilias Gialampoukidis³**, Stefanos Vrochidis³, Ioannis Kompatsiaris³, Konstantinos Demestichas⁴, Spyridon Kaloudis⁴, Roula Kechri⁵, Konstantinos Meletis⁵

¹ *Emergency Management and Civil Protection Sector, Center for Security Studies (Greece).*

(E-mail: g.sakkas@kemea-research.gr, v.varela@kemea-research.gr)

² *Hellenic Rescue Team (Greece).*

(E-mail: i.vourvachis@hrt.org.gr, a.giordanis@hrt.org.gr)

³ *Information Technologies Institute, Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (Greece).*

(E-mail: andreadisst@iti.gr, heliasgj@iti.gr, stefanos@iti.gr, ikom@iti.gr)

⁴ *Agricultural University of Athens (Greece).*

(E-mail: cdemest@aia.gr, kaloudis@aia.gr)

⁵ *Region of Central Greece*

(E-mail: kechri.r@pste.gov.gr, k.meletis@pste.gov.gr)

ABSTRACT

SILVANUS is a Green Deal EU funded project on preventing wildfires, that envisages to deliver an environmentally sustainable and climate resilient forest management platform through innovative capabilities to prevent and combat against the ignition and spread of forest fires. The project will test and validate its outcomes in eleven pilots, among which is North Evia in Greece. The project follows a holistic approach engaging stakeholders relevant to wildfire management through a participatory process. Currently, the project is at the beginning phase. Various technologies will be developed based on well-established and internationally accepted scientific methods. A workshop has already been organized in North Evia to discuss the problems that led to the recent extreme fire of 2021. Some preliminary results are briefly discussed.

Keywords: Wildfire management, early detection, efficient response, training, restoration, sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Wildfires are a complex phenomenon that depends mainly on vegetation, landscape, human activities and climate. Wildfires are becoming frequent and increasingly extreme, and according to [1], the recent extreme wildfires recorded globally between 2016 and 2020 are a consequence of climate processes due to climate change in relation to fuel mixture. According to [2], the summer season of 2021 was extreme in terms of wildfires in Greece, as the highest burned area since 2007 was recorded, mainly due to the wildfires in Evia island which burned over 51,000 ha, a large part of North Evia, resulting to a huge disaster, luckily without any death toll. In addition, large forest fires in Attica and Peloponnese in 2021 contributed to this extreme. Moreover, according to [3], the 2022 weekly cumulative number of forest fires in Greece is already above average.

SILVANUS (<https://silvanus-project.eu/>) is an EU Horizon 2020 Green Deal funded project that aims to create an innovative technological platform to support preparedness and response against wildfires. The project consists of 49 partners and was initiated in October 2021, with one of the main pilot areas being in Greece at Evia island. A significant number of SILVANUS consortium comes from Greece (EXUS, Agricultural University of Athens, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, University of Thessaly, Center for Security Studies, Center for Security Studies, Hellenic Rescue Team, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki-AHEPA, Region of Sterea Ellada). SILVANUS main objective is to support civil protection and

first responders' agencies through innovative technologies, increase citizen awareness with relevant training programmes, and improve the restoration and sustainability of forests. The project is currently in the first stages of its implementation and has already enabled a participatory process that engages multiple stakeholders for the development of a platform capable to cover the needs of the various agencies involved in the management of wildfires (before, during and after an incident). Moreover, a workshop has recently been organized in North Evia in order to discuss the problems that led to the burning of a massive area and reach a consensus about future actions.

2. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

A holistic approach is followed to prevent and suppress wildfires, including a high level of stakeholder engagement through a participatory process. From first responders to the health sector, from forest owners to the construction and energy industry, the SILVANUS platform (Figure 1) will address the needs and requirements of stakeholders by addressing the challenges outlined in each of the phases of disaster (phase A – Prevention and preparedness, phase B – Detection and response, phase C – Restoration and adaptation). Novel methodologies in monitoring and analysing ecological growth of natural resources will be developed to complement the analysis of biodiversity models. Cutting-edge technologies for the early-stage detection and response coordination of wildfire will supplement the environmental monitoring framework developed within SILVANUS, the platform will offer support for rehabilitation, restoration, and adaptation of natural forest growth. The SILVANUS forest management platform, along with its technologies and methodologies will be validated in 11 pilot areas worldwide. Eight of them are located in Europe (Greece, Italy, France, Portugal, Croatia, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Romania), while three are international (Australia, Indonesia and Brazil) pilot sites.

In particular, the Greek pilot site is Evia island and more specifically the Northern part and the three municipalities of Mantoudi-Limni-Ayia Anna, Istiaias-Aidipsou and Dirfis-Messapion (Figure 2). Evia is the second largest island in Greece and its total area is 4,167 km². About 2,500 km² of Evia is covered by forests, while the rest of the island consists of agricultural land, residential areas and barren rocky areas of high mountains.

In terms of climate, Evia has a wide climate variety that is due to its geographical location and the diversity of its terrain. The climate of Evia is of Mediterranean type, the rainfall season is recorded during the winter months, while in the summer months there is drought with high temperatures. Winters are mild and the average minimum temperature of the coldest month is 7°C. The prevailing climate conditions, in the wider area, can be described as very favourable for the existing forest vegetation in the area with several rains falling mainly during most of the germination period [4, 5]. The most significant forest species that constitute the forests of Evia are Aleppo pine (*Pinus halepensis*), Firs (*Abies sp.*), Black pine (*Pinus nigra*), Chestnut (*Castanea sativa*), Oak (*Quercus sp.*) and, sporadically, in small areas, other species, i.e., *Platanus orientalis* and *Accer sp.* The oak and fir forests, due to their small extent, have a minimal effect on the fire behaviour of the area.

Evia island is one of the most fire damaged in Greece. Frequent fires are the most serious risk of degradation of the forests. According to statistics, Evia is among the regions of Greece with the higher rate of yearly burned area. The most recent fire occurred is the mega-fire of 2021 that lasted for 10 days and burned more than 51,000 ha.

The SILVANUS platform will be installed to monitor and support activities in North Evia. During the project implementation period, the following functionalities and capabilities will be developed, tested and validated in the pilot site: fire vulnerability and risk maps, fire ignition - fire behaviour and propagation models, drone surveillance, social media sensing for early detection and warning through twitter, Decision Support System (DSS) for assisting response, training both for firefighters and citizens,

health metrics during a fire, soil protection measures and processes, forest restoration measures and activities, forest growth models, socio-cultural and local economy models, sustainability of actions, EU legislation and regulation for climate-related risks, policies for sustainable forests as well as ethical studies related to wildfire hazard.

Figure 1. The SILVANUS platform.

Figure 2. The SILVANUS Greek pilot study area.

Best practices related to both training of first responders and citizens will be applied. Innovative training that is related to the SILVANUS technologies and latest trends in training against natural disasters will be developed. SILVANUS will focus on enhancing citizen engagement and raising awareness activities in order to strengthen the interaction with local communities and their involvement in forest fire fighting. Info days will be carried out to educate them about safe forest behaviour and to train them on how to use the developed mobile application as well as on how they can support prevention efforts through its use. In addition, citizens will be educated on how they can help at all stages of a wildfire (before, during, and after an event). Such activities will be carried out in the areas of Evia and of Thessaloniki. Fire fighters will be trained on the use of the new technologies prior to pilot execution. One of the core technological advancements that will be exploited and evaluated in the Greek pilot is social media sensing, i.e., the monitoring of public social media posts from citizens or news on Twitter in order to timely detect potential cases of forest fire. Analysing the textual and visual information of the

tweets with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) can also provide further insight on the detected incidents, such as the location of the fire, the severity of the situation, whether humans are in danger etc. Even though social media sensing mainly supports phase B, by communicating crowdsourcing-detected fires as soon as possible to civil protection and first responders, contribution to phases A and C will also be investigated in SILVANUS. In phase A, social media could be monitored for discovering citizen recklessness that could lead to fires (e.g., people having a barbeque near the forest on a hot day), while in phase C for detecting unofficial/unorganized reforestation activities.

The technologies and scientific background of SILVANUS will be used in such a way that the platform can provide to all eleven pilots the same quality of results in a harmonized and reproducible manner, based on well-established scientific methodologies (e.g., [6]). SILVANUS aims to harmonize the various data streams into a unified data model (schema) that could fit the needs of any organization, site, or country.

3. DISCUSSION AND FIRST RESULTS

Recently a workshop has been held in North Evia, through a synergy between SILVANUS and two other EU funded projects, RISKPACC (<https://www.riskpacc.eu/>) and FireURisk (<https://fireurisk.eu/>). The workshop was planned and designed to gather local stakeholders (local civil protection agencies and municipalities, first responders, volunteer teams, high school students and teachers, and residents). Some of the initial outcomes include the need for reliable tools for early warning and detection, the importance of preparedness in order to build resilient forests and societies, the constant update of equipment, the regular training, the importance of having trained citizens and the measures to support restoration in a way that will sustain the nature. By the end of the project, the platform of SILVANUS will be capable of encompassing preparedness and response tools and restoration measures that will be supported from a policy perspective.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study has been conducted in the framework of SILVANUS project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101037247. The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.

REFERENCES

1. A. Duane, m. Castellnou, L. Brotons (2021). Towards a comprehensive look at global drivers of novel extreme wildfire events. *Climatic Change* 165, 43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-03066-4>.
2. J. San-Miguel-Ayanz, T. Durrant, R. Boca, P. Maiani, G. Libertà, T. Artés Vivancos, D. Oom, A. Branco, D. de Rigo, D. Ferrari, H. Pfeiffer, R. Grecchi, D. Nuijten (2022). Advance Report on Forest Fires in Europe, Middle East and North Africa 2021. Joint Research Centre technical report, European Commission. doi:10.2760/039729.
3. EFFIS statistics portal (<https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/apps/effis.statistics/seasonaltrend/GRC>). Last accessed 27 June 2022.
4. D. Stathis (2015). Lessons of forest meteorology (Mathimata dasikis meteorologias), Kallipos. ISBN: 978-960-603-179-3, p.240.
5. National Meteorological Organization portal: http://www.emy.gr/emy/el/climatology/climatology_city?perifereia=Sterea&poli=Skyros) Last accessed 27 June 2022.
6. C. E. Van Wagner (1987). The development and structure of the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System. Canadian Forest Service, Forest Technical Report 35. (Ottawa, ON).